

Big Data technologies: A Survey

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Abstract: This survey describes the concept of Big Data, which is non-conventional strategies and innovative technologies used by businesses and organizations to capture, manage, process, and make sense of a large volume of data. Traditional data techniques and platform are less efficient. Many companies are already trying to turn this Big Data to Big money. Firstly, definitions and features of Big Data. Secondly, Hortonworks Data Platform. Next, technologies are used to process Big Data. Finally, this survey describes the security of Big Data.

Keywords: Big Data; Hadoop Architecture; MapReduce

1. Introduction

These days, Massive data volumes are daily generated from different sources (health, marketing, financial, Science, Astronomy, Atmospheric Science, Genomics, Biogeochemical, Biological, Other complexes/ interdisciplinary, scientific research, Social, Social networks, Social data– Person to person (P2P, C2C. This is due to many technological trends, including internet of things (IoT), healthcare system. In 2018, 90% of the world's data was created in the last two years [1]. Massive challenges are in place with significant data like storage, transition, visualization, searching, analysis, security, and privacy violations, and sharing. Several researchers have highlighted the need for the research in big data, to manage the large datasets and a need for tools ranging from real-time processing to predictive analytics, data cleansing, and data visualization [2]. The following figure 1 refers to growing interconnected & instrumented world. Like our paper, they zoom on the concept of Big Data and technologies that it used. Before to Big Data revolution, companies could not store all their archives for long periods nor efficiently manage substantial data sets. Traditional technologies have limited storage capacity, rigid management tools, and are expensive. The shortage of scalability, flexibility, and performance needed in Big Data context. Big Data management requires significant resources, new methods, and powerful technologies. More precisely, Big Data requires to clean, process, analyze, secure, and provide granular access to big evolving data sets. Companies and industries are more aware that data analysis is increasingly becoming a vital factor to be competitive, to discover a new insight, and to personalize services [3]. To extract knowledge from Big Data, various models, programs, software, hardware, and technologies have been designed and proposed. They try to include more accurate and reliable results for Big Data applications. However, in such an environment, it may be time-consuming and challenging to choose among massive technologies. There exist many Big Data surveys in the literature, but most of them tend to focus on algorithms and approaches used to process Big Data rather than technologies. Therefore, this article defines *Big Data* (Section 2), Introduction to Hortonworks Data Platform (HDP)(Section 3), discuss Apache Ambari(Section 4), discuss

Hadoop and HDFS(section 5), discuss MapReduce and YARN(Section 6),discuss Apache Spark(Section 7),discuss Storing and querying data(Section 8),discuss Zookeeper, Slider, and Knox(Section 9), discuss Loading data with Sqoop(Section 10), discuss Security and Governance(Section 11), discuss Stream Computing(Section 12) and finally, discuss Big SQL(Section 13).

2. What is Big Data?

We are witnessing a tsunami of the enormous volume of data of different types and formats that make managing, processing, storing safeguarding and securing, and transporting them a real challenge. Big Data refers to non-conventional strategies and innovative technologies used

Fig. 1: Growing interconnected & instrumented world

Businesses and organizations to capture, manage, process, and make sense of a large volume of data [4]. Expansion in the smart electric meter market has cooled during the last year, even though active market drivers remain in place on which utilities can build a business case. Although the direct operational and societal benefits of smart meters and the broader benefits of smart grids that are enabled by smart meters continue to be debated among policymakers, utilities, regulators, and consumers, penetration rates go on the climb, reaching nearly 39 percent in North America in 2012. Number of monthly active Facebook users worldwide as of 1st quarter of 2016 (in millions) [5]. Mobile phones' numbers to exceed the world population by 2014. The ITU expects the number of cell phone accounts to rise from 6 billion now to 7.3 billion in 2014, compared with a global community of 7 billion. Over 100 countries have the number of cell phone accounts exceeding their population [6]. Cisco report says smartphone traffic will exceed PC traffic by 2020. IP traffic will grow in a massive way as 10 billion new devices come online over the next five years. Advancements in the Internet of Things (IoT) are continuing to drive IP traffic and tangible growth in the market [7]. Creating new network requirements and incremental traffic increases by Applications such as video surveillance, smart meters, digital health monitors, and a host of other Machine-to-Machine services.

Will reach 1.1 ZB per year or 88.7 EB (one billion gigabytes [GB]) per month in 2016 by Global IP traffic. Through 2020, global IP traffic will reach 2.3 ZB per year or 194 EB per month. The four standard dimensions of Big Data (4v) (volume, veracity, velocity, variety).

Volume. The main characteristic of big data is its huge volume collected through various sources. By Gigabytes or Terabytes, we are used to measuring data. However, according to multiple studies, big data volume created so far is in Zettabytes, which is equivalent to a trillion gigabytes. One zettabyte is equal to approximately 3 million galaxies of stars. This will give you an idea of the colossal volume of data being available for business research and analysis. Take any sector, and you can comprehend that it is flooded with loads of data. Travel, education, entertainment, health, banking, shopping - every sector can benefit immensely from the Big data advantage. Diverse sources which include business transactions, social media, sensors, surfing history (data is collected from it). With every passing day, data is growing exponentially. Thousands of TBs worth data is created every minute worldwide via Facebook, tweets, instant messages, email, internet usage, mobile usage, product reviews, etc. Every minute, hundreds of

twitter accounts are created, thousands of applications are downloaded, and thousands of new posts and ads are posted. According to experts, the amount of big data in the world is likely to get doubled every two years. This will definitely provide immense data in coming years and also calls for smarter data management. As the volume of the data is growing at the speed of light, traditional database technology will not suffice the need of efficient data management i.e. storage and analysis. The lack of the hour will be large-scale adoption of new-age tools like Hadoop and MongoDB. These use distributed systems to facilitate storage and analysis of this enormous big data across various databases. This information explosion has opened new doors of opportunities in the modern age.

Variety. Big data is collected and created in various formats and sources. It includes structured data as well as unstructured data like text, multimedia, social media, business reports, etc. Structured data such as bank records, demographic data, inventory databases, business data, product data feeds have a defined structure and can be stored and analyzed using traditional data management and analysis methods. Unstructured data includes captured like images, tweets, or Facebook status updates, instant messenger conversations, blogs, videos uploads, voice recordings, sensor data. These types of data do not have any defined pattern. Unstructured data is most of the time reflection of human thoughts, emotions, and feelings, which sometimes would be difficult to be expressed using exact words. As the saying goes, "A picture paints a thousand words," one image or video which is shared on social networking sites and applauded by millions of users can help in deriving some crucial inferences. Hence, it is the need of the hour to understand this non-verbal language to unlock some secrets of market trends. One of the main objectives of big data is to collect all this unstructured data and analyze it using the appropriate technology. Data crawling, also known as web crawling, is an accessible technology used for systematically browsing the web pages. There are algorithms designed to reach the maximum depth of a page and extract useful data worth analyzing. Variety of data helps to get insights from a different set of samples, users, and demographics. It helps to bring a different view of the same information. It also allows analyzing and understanding the impact of varying form and sources of data collection from a 'larger picture' point of view. For instance, to recognize the performance of a brand, traditional surveys are one of the forms of data collection. This is done by selecting a sample, mostly from panels. The advantage of this approach is that you get direct answers to the questions. However, we can obtain real-time feedback through various other forms like Facebook activity, product review blogs, and updates posted by customers on merchant websites like Flipkart, Amazon, and Snapdeal. A combination of these two forms of data gives a data-backed, clearer perspective to your business decision-making process.

Velocity. In today's fast-paced world, speed is one of the critical drivers for success in your business as time is equivalent to money. A fast turn-around is one of the pre-requisites to stay alive in this fierce competition. Expectations of quick results and quick deliverables are pressing to a great extent. In such scenarios, it becomes vital to collect and analyze the vast amount of disparate data swiftly, to make well-informed decisions in real-time. Low velocity of even high quality of data may hinder the decision making of a business. The general definition of Velocity is 'speed in a specific direction.' In big data, Velocity is the speed or frequency at which data is collected in various forms and from different sources for processing. The rate of specific data collected via multiple sources defines the velocity of that data. In other terms, it is data in motion to be captured and explored. It ranges from batch updates, to periodic to the real-time flow of the data. The frequency of Facebook status updates shared, and messages tweeted every second, videos uploaded and/or downloaded every minute, or the online/offline bank transactions recorded every hour, determine the velocity of the data. You can relate velocity with the amount of trade information captured

during each trading session in a stock exchange. Imagine a video or an image going viral at the blink of an eye to reaching millions of users across the world. Big data technology allows you to process the real-time data, sometimes without even capturing in a database. Streams of data are processed, and databases are updated in real-time, using parallel processing of live streams of data. Data streaming helps extract valuable insights from incessant and rapid flow of data records. A streaming application like Amazon Web Services (AWS) *Kinesis* is an example of an application that handles the velocity of data. The higher the frequency of data collection into your big data platform in a stipulated period, the more likely it will enable you to make an accurate decision at the right time.

Veracity. The fascinating trio of volume, variety, and velocity of data brings along a mixed bag of information. Such massive data may have some uncertainty associated with it. You will need to filter out clean and relevant data from big data, to provide insights that power up your business. To make accurate decisions, the data you have used as input should be appropriately compiled, confirmed, validated, and made uniform. There are various reasons of data contamination like data entry errors or typos (mostly in structured data), wrong references or links, junk data, pseudo data, etc. The enormous volume, wide variety, and high velocity in conjunction with high-end technology, holds no significance if the data collected or reported is incorrect. Hence, data trustworthiness (in other words, quality of data) holds the highest importance in the big data world. In automated data collection, analysis, report generation, and decision-making process, it is inevitable to have a foolproof system in place to avoid any lapses. Even the most minor of slippage at any stage in the big data extraction process can cause enormous blunder. Any reports generated based on a specific type of data from a particular source must be validated for accuracy and reliability. It is always advisable that you have two different methods and sources to validate the credibility and consistency of the data, to avoid any bias. It is not only about precision post data collection, but also, about determining right source and form of the data, required amount or size of the data, and the right method of analysis, play a vital role in procuring impeccable results. Integrity in any field of business life or personal life holds the highest significance, and hence, proper measures must be put in place to take care of this crucial aspect. It will allow you to position yourself in the market as a reliable authority and help you to attain greater heights of success. These 4v's are like four pillars lending stability to the giant structure of big data and adding a precious 5th "V" - value - to the information procured leads to the whole purpose of big data, smart decision making.

3. Hortonworks Data Platform (HDP)

Hortonworks Data Platform (HDP) is a powerful platform for managing Big Data at rest. HDP is Open Enterprise Hadoop, and it's a platform that is: 100% Open Source, centrally architected with YARN at its core, Interoperable with existing technology and skills AND Enterprise-ready with data services for operations, governance, and security. Figure 2 refers to a high-level view of the Hortonworks Data Platform. It is divided into several categories, listed in no particular order of importance. Governance, integration, tools, security, operations, data access, and data management.

Fig. 2: HDP

4. Apache Ambari

Making Hadoop management more straightforward by developing software for provisioning, managing, and monitoring Apache Hadoop clusters (The Apache Ambari project). Ambari provides an intuitive, easy-to-use Hadoop management web user interface (UI) backed by its RESTful APIs. The functionality of Apache Ambari enables system administrators to provision a Hadoop, manage a Hadoop cluster, monitor a Hadoop cluster and enables application developers and system integrators to easily integrate Hadoop provisioning, management, and monitoring capabilities to their applications with the Ambari REST APIs [8] (Ambari). One of the more fascinating pieces of Ambari is its Ambari Metrics System. The Ambari Metrics System ("AMS") is a system for collecting, aggregating and serving Hadoop and system metrics in Ambari-managed clusters. The Ambari Server also contains or interacts with the following components: Postgres RDBMS (default) stores the cluster configurations, Authorization Provider, integrates with an organization's authentication/authorization provider such as the LDAP service (By default Ambari uses an internal database as the user store for authentication and authorization), Ambari Alert Framework supports alerts and notifications and REST API integrates with the web-based front-end Ambari Web. Custom applications can also use this REST API.

5. Hadoop and HDFS

There has been much buzz about Hadoop and big data in the marketplace over the past year, with Wikibon predicting a \$50B marketplace by 2017. Hortonworks says on their web site that they believe that half of the world's data will be stored in Hadoop within the next 5 years. With so much at stake, there are a lot of vendors looking for some of the action and the big database vendors are not standing still. Open source project of the Apache Foundation (Hadoop). Developed by Doug Cutting who named it after his son's toy elephant and framework written in Java originally (Hadoop). Hadoop uses Google's MapReduce and Google File System (GFS) technologies as its foundation. It is optimized to handle massive amounts of data

which could be structured, unstructured or semi-structured, and uses commodity hardware (relatively inexpensive computers). This huge parallel processing is done with great performance. However, it is a batch operation handling huge amounts of data, so the response time is not immediate. As of Hadoop version 0.20.2, updates are not possible, but appends were made possible starting in version 0.21. What is the value of a system if the information it stores or retrieves is not consistent? Hadoop replicates its data across various computers, so that if one goes down, the data is processed on one of the replicated computers. You may be familiar with OLTP (Online Transactional processing) workloads where data is randomly accessed on structured data like a relational database, such as when you access your bank account. You may also be familiar with OLAP (Online Analytical processing) or DSS (Decision Support Systems) workloads where data is sequentially access on structured data, like a relational database, to generate reports that provide business intelligence. You may not be that familiar with the concept of big data. Big data is a term used to describe large collections of data (also known as datasets) that may be unstructured, and grow so large and quickly that is difficult to manage with regular database or statistics tools. Hadoop is not used for OLTP nor OLAP, but is used for big data, and it complements these two to manage data. Hadoop is not a replacement for a RDBMS. Hadoop is cannot resolve all data-related problems. It is being designed to handle big data. Hadoop works better when handling one single huge file rather than many small files. Hadoop complements existing RDBMS technology. Wikipedia: allows human-unnoticeable delays between an input being processed and the corresponding output providing real time characteristics (Low latency). Internet connections utilizing services such as online gaming and VOIP this (Low latency) can be especially important for it. Hadoop is not good for low latency data access. In practice you can replace latency with delay. So low latency means negligible delay in processing. Low latency data access means negligible delay accessing data. Hadoop is not designed for low latency. Hadoop works best with very large files. The larger the file, the less time Hadoop spends seeking for the next data location on disk and the more time Hadoop runs at the limit of the bandwidth of your disks. When you only need to analyze a small subset of your dataset seeks are generally expensive operations and useful. It is best to minimize seeks by using large files, since Hadoop is designed to run over your entire dataset. Hadoop is good for applications requiring high throughput of data: Clustered machines can read data in parallel for high throughput. There are two aspects of Hadoop that are important to understand: A. MapReduce is a software framework introduced by Google to support distributed computing on large data sets of clusters of computers. B. The Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) is where Hadoop stores its data. This file system spans all the nodes in a cluster. Effectively, links together the data that resides on many local nodes, making the data part of one big file system (HDFS). HDFS is quite common file system that you can use it with Hadoop. The driving principle of MapReduce is a simple one: spread the data out across a huge cluster of machines and then, rather than bringing the data to your programs as you do in a traditional programming, write your program in a specific way that allows the program to be moved to the data. Thus, the entire cluster is made available in both reading the data as well as processing the data. The Distributed File System (DFS) is at the heart of MapReduce. It is responsible for spreading data across the cluster, by making the entire cluster look like one giant file system. When a file is written to the cluster, blocks of the file are spread out and replicated across the whole cluster (in the diagram, notice that every block of the file is replicated to three different machines). Adding more nodes to the cluster instantly adds capacity to the file system and automatically increases the available processing power and parallelism. HDFS consists from Name Node and Data Node. Name Node consists from FSImage and EditsLog. FSImage is a file stores the entire file system namespace, including the mapping of blocks to files and file system properties. The Name Node's local file system stores FSImage as a file. It contains the metadata on

disk (not exact copy of what is in RAM, but a checkpoint copy). The Name Node uses a transaction log called the EditLog (or Edits Log) to persistently record every change that occurs to file system metadata, synchronizes with metadata in RAM after each write. The Name Node can be a potential single point of failure (this has been resolved in later releases of HDFS with Secondary Name Node, various forms of high availability, and in Hadoop v2 with Name Node federation and high availability as out-of-the-box options). Use better quality hardware for all management nodes, and in particular do not use inexpensive commodity hardware for the Name Node. Mitigate by backing up to other storage. In case of power failure on Name Node, recover is performed using the FsImage and the EditLog. Smaller pieces (called blocks), data in a Hadoop cluster is broken down in it and distributed throughout the cluster. In this way, Functions can be executed on smaller subsets of your larger data sets, and this provides the scalability that is needed for big data processing (map and reduce) [9].

6. MapReduce and YARN

The driving principle of MapReduce is a simple one: spread your data out across a huge cluster of machines and then, rather than bringing the data to your programs as you do in traditional programming, you write your program in a specific way that allows the program to be moved to the data. Thus, the entire cluster is made available in both reading the data as well as processing the data. A Distributed File System (DFS) is at the heart of MapReduce. It is responsible for spreading data across the cluster, by making the entire cluster look like one giant file system. When a file is written to the cluster, blocks of the file are spread out and replicated across the whole cluster (in the diagram, notice that every block of the file is replicated to three different machines). Adding more nodes to the cluster instantly adds capacity to the file system and, as we'll see on the next slide, automatically increases the available processing power and parallelism. MapReduce consists from JobTracker and TaskTracker. Accepts MapReduce jobs submitted by clients, pushes map and reduce tasks out to TaskTracker nodes, keeps the work as physically close to data as possible and monitors tasks and TaskTracker status (JobTracker). TaskTracker runs map and reduce tasks, reports status to JobTracker and manages storage and transmission of intermediate output. It can retard the entire MapReduce job, if one TaskTracker is very slow, especially towards the end of a job, where everything can end up waiting for the slowest task. A single task can be executed on multiple slave nodes with speculative-execution enabled. For jobs scheduling, by default Hadoop uses FIFO (First in, First Out), and optional 5 scheduling priorities to schedule jobs from a work queue. Other scheduling algorithms are available as add-ins: Fair Scheduler, Capacity Scheduler, and so on. A framework for processing massive datasets on certain kinds of distributable problems using a large number of computers (nodes), collectively referred to as a cluster (if all nodes use the same hardware) or as a grid (if the nodes use different hardware) (MapReduce). Computational processing can occur on data stored either in a file system (unstructured) or within a database (structured) [10]. Map phase, A mapper is typically a relatively small program with a relatively simple task: it is responsible for reading a portion of the input data, interpreting, filtering or transforming the data as necessary and then finally producing a stream of <key, value> pairs. What these keys and values are is not of importance in the scope of this topic, but just keep in mind that these values can be as big and complex as you need. Shuffle phase, the output of each mapper is locally grouped together by key, one node is chosen to process data for each unique key and all of this movement (shuffle) of data is transparently orchestrated by MapReduce. Reduce phase, Reducers: Small programs (typically) that aggregate all of the values for the key that they are responsible for and each reducer writes output to its own file. Combiner phase(optional), the data that will go to each reduce node is sorted and merged before going to the reduce node, pre-doing some of the work of the receiving reduce node in order to minimize

network traffic between map and reduce nodes. Issues with the original MapReduce paradigm: centralized handling of job control flow and tight coupling of a specific programming model with the resource management infrastructure. Split up the two major functionalities of the JobTracker, resource management and job scheduling/monitoring, into separate daemons (fundamental idea of YARN/MRv2), that have a global ResourceManager (RM) and per application ApplicationMaster (AM). Either a single job in the classical sense of Map-Reduce jobs or a DAG of jobs (An application). The data computation framework is formed from the ResourceManager and per-node slave, the NodeManager (NM). Ultimate authority that arbitrates resources among all the applications in the system (ResourceManager). In effect, a framework specific library and is tasked with negotiating resources from the ResourceManager and working with the NodeManager(s) to execute and monitor the tasks (The per-application ApplicationMaster). The ResourceManager has two main components: Scheduler and ApplicationsManager [11]. Responsible for allocating resources to the various running applications subject to familiar constraints of capacities, queues etc (The Scheduler). Pure scheduler in the sense that it performs no monitoring or tracking of status for the application (The Scheduler). Also, it offers no guarantees about restarting failed tasks either due to application failure or hardware failures. Performs its scheduling function based the resource requirements of the applications; it does so based on the abstract notion of a resource Container which incorporates elements such as memory, CPU, disk, network etc (The Scheduler). In the first version, only memory is supported. The Scheduler has a pluggable policy plug-in, which is responsible for partitioning the cluster resources among the various queues, applications etc. The current MapReduce schedulers such as the Capacity Scheduler and the Fair Scheduler would be some examples of the plug-in. The Capacity Scheduler supports hierarchical queues to allow for more predictable sharing of cluster resources. The ApplicationsManager is responsible for accepting job-submissions, negotiating the first container for executing the application specific ApplicationMaster and provides the service for restarting the ApplicationMaster container on failure. The NodeManager is the per-machine framework agent who is responsible for containers, monitoring their resource usage (CPU, memory, disk, and network) and reporting the same to the ResourceManager/Scheduler. The ApplicationMaster has the responsibility of negotiating appropriate resource containers from the Scheduler, tracking their status and monitoring for progress. MRV2 maintains API compatibility with previous stable release (hadoop-1.x). This means that all Map-Reduce jobs should still run unchanged on top of MRv2 with just a recompile. YARN features: scalability, multi-tenancy, compatibility, serviceability, higher cluster utilization and reliability/availability. The most notable change from Hadoop v1 to Hadoop v2 is the separation of cluster and resource management from the execution and data processing environment. This allows for a new variety of application types to run, including MapReduce v2. In MapReduce v1 there is just one JobTracker that is responsible for allocation of resources, task assignment to data nodes (as TaskTrackers), and ongoing monitoring ("heartbeat") as each job is run (the TaskTrackers constantly report back to the JobTracker on the status of each running task). In the YARN architecture, a global ResourceManager runs as a master daemon, usually on a dedicated machine, that arbitrates the available cluster resources among various competing applications. The ResourceManager tracks how many live nodes and resources are available on the cluster and coordinates what applications submitted by users should get these resources and when. The ResourceManager is the single process that has this information so it can make its allocation (or rather, scheduling) decisions in a shared, secure, and multi-tenant manner (for instance, according to an application priority, a queue capacity, ACLs, data locality, etc.). When a user submits an application, an instance of a lightweight process called the ApplicationMaster is started to coordinate the execution of all tasks within the application. This includes monitoring tasks, restarting failed tasks, speculatively running

slow tasks, and calculating total values of application counters. These responsibilities were previously assigned to the single JobTracker for all jobs. The ApplicationMaster and tasks that belong to its application run in resource containers controlled by the NodeManagers. The NodeManager is a more generic and efficient version of the TaskTracker. Instead of having a fixed number of map and reduce slots, the NodeManager has a number of dynamically created resource containers. The size of a container depends upon the amount of resources it contains, such as memory, CPU, disk, and network IO. Currently, only memory and CPU (YARN-3) are supported. Cgroups might be used to control disk and network IO in the future. The number of containers on a node is a product of configuration parameters and the total amount of node resources (such as total CPUs and total memory) outside the resources dedicated to the slave daemons and the OS. Interestingly, the ApplicationMaster can run any type of task inside a container. For example, the MapReduce ApplicationMaster requests a container to launch a map or a reduce task, while the Giraph ApplicationMaster requests a container to run a Giraph task. You can also implement a custom ApplicationMaster that runs specific tasks and, in this way, invent a shiny new distributed application framework that changes the big data world. I encourage you to read about Apache Twill, which aims to make it easy to write distributed applications sitting on top of YARN. In YARN, MapReduce is simply degraded to a role of a distributed application (but still a very popular and useful one) and is now called MRv2. MRv2 is simply the re-implementation of the classical MapReduce engine, now called MRv1, which runs on top of YARN. YARN: acronym for Yet Another Resource Negotiator, new resource manager included in Hadoop 2.x and later, de-couples Hadoop workload and resource management, introduces a general-purpose application container, Hadoop 2.2.0 includes the first GA version of YARN and Most Hadoop vendors support YARN.

7. Apache Spark

There is an explosion of data, and no matter where you look, data is everywhere. You get data from social media such as Twitter feeds, Facebook posts, SMS, and a variety of others. The need to be able to process those data as quickly as possible becomes more important than ever. How can you find out what your customers want and be able to offer it to them right away? You do not want to wait hours for a batch job to complete; you need to have it in minutes or less. MapReduce has been useful, but the amount of time it takes for the jobs to run is no longer acceptable in many situations. The learning curve to writing a MapReduce job is also difficult as it takes specific programming knowledge and expertise. Also, MapReduce jobs only work for a specific set of use cases. You need something that works for a wider set of use cases. Apache Spark was designed as a computing platform to be fast, general-purpose, and easy to use. Apache Spark extends the MapReduce model and takes it to a whole other level. The speed comes from the in-memory computations. Applications running in memory allows for a much faster processing and response. Spark is even faster than MapReduce for complex applications on disk. This generality covers a wide range of workloads under one system. You can run batch application such as MapReduce type jobs or iterative algorithms that builds upon each other. With your application, you can also run interactive queries and process streaming data. In a later slide, you'll see that there are a number of libraries which you can easily use to expand beyond the basic Spark capabilities. The ease of use with Spark enables you to quickly pick it up using simple APIs for Scala, Python, Java, and R. As mentioned, there are additional libraries which you can use for SQL, machine learning, streaming, and graph processing. Spark runs on Hadoop clusters such as Hadoop YARN or Apache Mesos, or even as a standalone with its own scheduler. Spark is related to MapReduce in a sense that it expands on Hadoop's capabilities. Like MapReduce, Spark provides parallel distributed processing, fault tolerance on commodity hardware, scalability, etc. Spark

adds to the concept with aggressively cached in-memory distributed computing, low latency, high level APIs and stack of high-level tools described on the next slide. This saves time and money. Spark simplifies the picture by providing many of Hadoop ecosystem functions through several purpose-built components. These are Spark Core, Spark SQL, Spark Streaming, Spark MLlib, and Spark GraphX

8. Storing and querying data

Storing petabytes of data in Hadoop is relatively easy, but it is more important to choose an efficient storage format for faster querying. Row-based encodings (Text, Avro, JSON) with a general-purpose compression library (gzip, LZO, CMX, Snappy) are common mainly for interoperability reasons, but column-based storage formats (Parquet, ORC) provide not only faster query execution by minimizing IO but also great compression. Compression is important to big data file storage: reduces file sizes and thus speeds up transfer to/from disk and generally faster to transfer a small file and then decompress than to transfer a larger file.

9. Zookeeper, Slider, and Knox

ZooKeeper provides support for writing distributed applications in the Hadoop ecosystem. ZooKeeper addresses the issue of partial failure: partial failure is intrinsic to distributed systems and ZK provides a set of tools to build distributed applications that can safely handle partial failures. ZooKeeper has the following characteristics: simple, expressive, highly available, facilitates loosely coupled interactions and is a library. Apache ZooKeeper is an open source server that enables highly reliable distributed coordination [12]. ZooKeeper: distributed applications require coordination and distributed open-source centralized coordination service. The ZooKeeper service is distributed, reliable, fast, and simple. A YARN application to deploy existing distributed applications on YARN, monitor them and make them larger or smaller as desired, even while the application is running (Apache Slider). Some of the features are: allows users to create on-demand applications in a YARN cluster, allows different users/applications to run different versions of the application, allows users to configure different application instances differently, stop/restart application instances as needed, expand/shrink application instances as needed. The Slider tool is a Java command line application. YARN resource management and scheduling works well for batch workloads, but not for interactive or real-time data processing services. Apache Slider extends YARN to support long-running distributed services on a Hadoop cluster: dynamic expansion or contraction of services, dedicated monitoring and supports restart after process failure. Live Long and Process (LLAP). The Apache Knox Gateway is an extensible reverse proxy framework for securely exposing REST APIs and HTTP based services at a perimeter.

10. Loading data with Sqoop

Several load scenarios: data at rest, data in motion, data from web server and database logs and data from a data warehouse. Data at rest is already in a file in some directory. No additional updates are planned on this data and it can be transferred as is. This can be accomplished using standard HDFS shell commands, put, cp or copyFromLocal, or using the HDP web console. Data in motion: Data from multiple locations that needs to be merged into one single source for example: merge all log files from one directory into one file. Data from a web server: If the source is from a web server such as WebSphere, Data is typically web server logs or applications logs and Logs are constantly appended. Data from a Data Warehouse or RDBMS: Use standard database export commands, export the tables into comma delimited files & and then use Hadoop commands to import the data HDFS, Sqoop to load directly from relational systems, Data from

Db2 and Netezza, using proprietary stored procedures and the like and Data from Db2, Netezza, Teradata, and other database servers into Big SQL using Big SQL Load. Sqoop transfers data between Hadoop and relational databases, Uses the database to describe the schema of the data, Uses MapReduce to import and export the data, can help you to quickly develop MapReduce applications that use HDFS-stored records and the options import and export work in relation to HDFS (and the opposite of the relation to the database itself). Flume has agents, installed at a source, which only know how to read data and pass it on to a sink. A source can be a file, a stream or it might be another Flume agent. Likewise the sink might be, among other things, HDFS or another Flume agent. The final agent in the chain is the collector.

11. Security and Governance

The need for data Governance: data governance → Data reliability: accurate analysis & reporting, confident decision making and reduce unwanted financial outlays and functionality requirement: discover & Understand (embody the “data guru”), define the Metadata, handle Security, provide Privacy, Maintain Data integrity and measure & Monitor [13]. Hadoop security requires strong authentication, strong authorization, isolation between running tasks and ongoing development priority & commitment. HDP ensures comprehensive enforcement of security requirements across the entire Hadoop stack. Kerberos is the key to strong authentication. Ranger provides a single simple interface for security policy definition and maintenance. Encryption options available for data at-rest and in-motion. Enterprise security services HDP: centralized security administration, authentication, authorization, audit and data Protection. Authentication: Who am I? How can I prove it? (Kerberos API security with Apache Knox). Authorization: What can I do? (Fine grained access control with Apache Ranger). Audit: What did the users do? (Centralized audit reporting with Apache Ranger). Data Protection: Can I encrypt data in transit & at rest? (Wire encryption for data in transit and •Disk encryption in Hadoop) [14].

12. Stream Computing

Applications that require on-the-fly processing, filtering, and analysis of streaming data Sensors: environmental, industrial, surveillance video, GPS, ..., Data exhaust: network/system/webserver log files and high-rate transaction data: financial transactions, call detail records. Criteria: two or more of the following: messages are processed in isolation or in limited data windows, sources include non-traditional data (spatial, imagery, text, ...), sources vary in connection methods, data rates, and processing requirements, that present integration challenges, data rates / volumes require the resources of multiple processing nodes, analysis and response are needed with sub-millisecond latency and data rates and volumes are too great for store-and-mine approaches [15].

13. Big SQL

Big SQL builds on an Apache Hive foundation. Hive consists of an execution engine, a storage model, and a metastore. This metastore tracks all the metadata about tables within Hadoop, and is used by multiple projects within the Hadoop ecosystem. Big SQL provides you with an alternate execution engine, which has many advantages when compared to Hive to accommodate a variety of workloads. Big SQL shines with high concurrency workloads, complex SQL, data virtualization, and more. Rather than using MapReduce (which Hive uses), Big SQL uses a powerful, native MPP engine, written in C/C++. Big SQL shares metadata with Hive using the same data on disk and same definition of tables within the metastore. A table in Hive can be seen in Big SQL and vice-versa. Think of Big SQL as a logical view on top of your Hadoop data. The data resides in Hadoop and all you have to do is use Big SQL to access it. There is no

need to change the format, or migrate the data out of Hadoop to do any work on the data. Big SQL supports modern SQL: 2011 capabilities. So, when you migrate your data into Hadoop, the same SQL can be used on your warehouse data with little or no modification. That is one of the big benefits of Big SQL - no need to learn anything new, and can use your existing queries. There are a number of tools available to work with data on Hadoop. Tools such as MapReduce, Pig, Hive, and many more. MapReduce, being one of the most common tools is highly scalable, but it is difficult to use. There are a lot of coding required for running batch jobs. There are other tools as well, but those all require a specific set of expertise. What Big SQL offers is a common and familiar query syntax that everybody understands.

14. Conclusion

Big Data is supported by different technologies and tools to process it and extract value. This paper discussed 4v of Big Data. 4v is volume, variety, velocity and veracity. Volume the main characteristic of big data is its huge volume collected through various sources. Variety that Big data is collected and created in various formats and sources. It includes structured data as well as unstructured data like text, multimedia, social media, business reports etc. Velocity is the speed or frequency at which data is collected in various forms and from different sources for processing. Veracity is the quality or trustworthiness of the data. In addition to that, we studies technologies of Big Data. Besides, we have explained component of Hadoop.

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